

Physico-chemical Study of the Interaction of Iron and Aluminium with Sodium Pyrophosphate in Water-alcohol and Water-dioxane Media

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The composition of aluminium and iron pyrophosphate complexes in water, water-alcohol and water dioxane medium was determined by *pH*-metric, conductometric and amperometric methods. Conductometric titrations showed the existence of 2:3, 4:3, 2:1 complexes in aqueous, 4:3, 2:1, 1:1 in water-alcohol and 2:1, 1:1 in water dioxane media. The *pH*-metric and amperometric titrations were successful only in water-alcohol and water-dioxane media where 2:1 and 1:1 complexes were formed.

No clear picture of the nature and composition of the pyrophosphates of aluminium and iron is available from the existing literature on the subject. The investigations of Rogers and Reynolds¹, Subrahmanya², Banerjee and Mitra³, and Friksson⁴ point towards the existence of four or five complexes. Since all these investigations were carried out in the aqueous medium, factors like the hydrolysis of the reaction products, their solubility and tendency of co-precipitation could not be controlled. Interference by these factors becomes all the more evident when using conductometric methods for investigating the composition. However, difficulties can be overcome by carrying out investigations in non-aqueous or partially aqueous medium. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to work on the composition of aluminium and iron pyrophosphate complexes applying electrometric titration methods in partially aqueous medium. Both the *pH* metric and amperometric methods could be successfully employed to elucidate the composition of the complexes, confirmation by conductometric methods could only be achieved in dioxane medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents: Ferric chloride, aluminium nitrate and all other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Double distilled methyl alcohol and dioxane were used for the preparation of solutions. Potassium acid phthalate was used for the preparation of standard buffer of *pH* 4.

Apparatus: *pH*-metric titrations were carried out by using Cambridge Bench type *pH* meter with glass and calomel electrodes.

Conductometric measurements were carried out with Phillips Conductivity Bridge using a dip type conductivity cell.

1. L. B. Rogers and C. A. Reynolds, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2081.
2. R. S. Subrahmanya, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1956, **38**, 87-95.
3. S. Banerjee and S. K. Mitra, *Science and Culture*, 1951, **16**, 530-1.
4. Erik Friksson Kgl. Lantbruks, Hoskol, *Ann.*, 1949, **16**, 39-48.

Amperometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal Polarograph (India) using Scalamp Galvanometer (W. G. Pye), D.M.E. and S.C.E. Triple distilled mercury was used for the dropping mercury electrode. The solutions were deaerated by using purified nitrogen for about twenty minutes in the polarographic cell. All measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in a water thermostat. The capillary used had the following characteristics in the open circuit:

$$t = 3.5 \text{ sec.}, \quad m = 5.54 \text{ mg/sec.}^{-1}; \quad m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 3.88$$

The strength of the stock solution of ferric chloride was determined iodometrically⁵ and of aluminium nitrate with standard sodium hydroxide at boiling temperature using phenolphthalein indicator⁶. Ferric chloride solution was prepared purely in methyl alcohol and in dioxane but aluminium nitrate and sodium pyrophosphate were in methyl alcohol or dioxane containing minimum possible percentage of double distilled water to keep the solution clear. Since the solution of sodium pyrophosphate did not remain stable for a long time, fresh solutions were prepared when required.

The amperometric titrations were carried out at -1.5 V (potential at the plateau of ferric chloride polarogram in dioxane medium using lithium chloride as supporting electrolyte) and at -1.8 V (potential at the plateau of ferric chloride polarogram in aqueous medium using KCl as the supporting electrolyte). A series of solutions were made up, each of which contains a different concentration of ferric chloride and then titrated with sodium-pyrophosphate.

RESULTS

Resistance studies: In aqueous medium the observed inflexion points at 0.2, 0.4 and 0.6 ml. Fig. 1(a) correspond to the formation of complex ions $(\text{Fe}_2(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_3)^{-6}$, $(\text{Fe}_4(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_3)$ and $(\text{Fe}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)^{+2}$. In the water alcohol medium [Fig. 1 (d & e)] two inflexions were obtained at 0.4 and 0.6 ml. corresponding to the formation of $(\text{Fe}_4(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_3)$ and $(\text{Fe}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)^{+2}$ in the direct titration and one at 0.3 ml. in the reverse titration for the formation of the complex $(\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7)^{-}$. In the water-dioxane medium again two inflexion points at 0.3 and 0.6 ml. respectively are realised [Fig. 1(c)]. Similar results were obtained from the titration curves of aluminium nitrate against sodium pyrophosphate but no sharp inflexion point was realised in the water-dioxane medium.

Amperometric Studies: Amperometric titrations in the aqueous medium carried out by adding sodium pyrophosphate to ferric chloride (in the polarographic cell) gave the two inflexion points, the first corresponding to the stoichiometric ratios Fe^{+++} to $\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$, as 2.5:1 was not sharp [Fig. 3(a)]. This inflexion became very distinct in the water dioxane and water alcohol media, the combining ratio being shifted to 2 : 1. The ratio for the second inflexion

5. A. I. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", p. 372 (1961).

6. Alex Charles Cumming and Sydney Alexander Kay, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis" p. 95-96, (1948).

1 : 1 remained the same both in the aqueous and partially aqueous medium, (Fig. 3). The reactions which proceed during the course of these titrations may be represented as follows:

When $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ is added in large excess, compound II is formed. After the formation of compound I, current does not become constant due to further interaction with the sodium pyrophosphate and the current decreases. After compound II has been formed the current becomes constant.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2A

pH-Metric Studies: In direct titrations, (ferric chloride was added to pyrophosphate [Fig. 2A, curve(a)], the initial pH of the sodium pyrophosphate solution is very high because of hydrolysis

When ferric chloride is added, hydrogen ions are liberated, hence pH decreases. In the beginning pH decreases very slowly. After the addition of one equivalent of ferric chloride,

there is a sudden decrease in pH . It seems that H^+ ion liberated during the course of the reaction first neutralise the OH^-

FIGURE 2B

FIGURE 3

As the ferric chloride is added in increasing amount there is a liberation of hydrogen ions, hence pH decreases gradually and after the addition of two equivalents of ferric chloride, a hump in pH was observed.

In reverse titrations, on addition of sodium pyrophosphate in increasing amount, there is no increase in $p\text{H}$ in the beginning and remains almost constant until $\text{Fe}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7(\text{OH})_2$ is formed. On further addition $p\text{H}$ increases very rapidly and go on increasing, until $2(\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7)^-$ is formed. The rise in $p\text{H}$ after the formation of $(\text{Fe}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)^{2+}$ is simply due to the gradual addition of the pyrophosphate solution, the hydrolysis of which causes such sharp rise in $p\text{H}$ from 4 to 9. The stoichiometric reaction may be represented as follows:

Similar behaviour is observed in $p\text{H}$ -metric titrations of aluminium nitrate with sodium pyrophosphate in water-dioxane medium.

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Received, April 4, 1966.